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Impact Of LinkedIn On The Job Market – Need For A Better Alternative?

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Abstract

This study explores the perceived effectiveness of using LinkedIn as a professional networking platform and job-search platform among Indian job seekers. Despite significant penetration of LinkedIn in India, there remains limited empirical research assessing its utility within its unique and rapidly evolving job market. Primary data was collected from 75 respondents via structured online surveys. The analysis revealed that while LinkedIn is widely used and valued for its networking capabilities and professional visibility, users report challenges such as high competition, limited recruiter responsiveness and prevalence of fake job postings. The study also analyzed the effectiveness of premium features. A significant portion of respondents expressed interest in alternative platforms features such as enhanced transparency, real time application status tracking and more effective recruiter-applicant interactions. The study also identifies the growing acceptance of AI-based job matching and gamification as desirable innovations. These findings underscore the need for a more inclusive, responsive and technologically adaptive platform to support the changing job environment in India.

Keywords LinkedIn, Job search, Professional networking, Recruiter engagement, Indian job marke

Introduction

Industry Overview

LinkedIn is a business and employment oriented social network. It was launched on May 5, 2003 by Reid Hoffman and Eric Ly (Wikipedia, 2004). With over 1 billion members, its goal is to enable registered members to establish and document professional networks of people they know and trust. It is also a resource for professionals to find jobs, research companies, get news about their industry, make business connections and participate in online training. (Mary E. Shacklett, 2025). About 134.5 million users actively use LinkedIn each day. Additionally, over 48.5% are active monthly. (Jack Shepherd, 2025). As of February 2025, LinkedIn had an audience of 250 million in the United States. The country was the leading market of professional networking service, followed by India and Brazil, with 150 million and 81 million users, respectively. As of early 2025, almost half of LinkedIn's global users were aged between 25 and 34 years. Additionally, 56.9 % of LinkedIn users were men. (Statista, 2025). Millennial make up 60% of LinkedIn's users. In addition, about 20% of users are between 18 and 24, and almost 18% are between 35 and 54. Only 2% are 55 and older (Jack Shepherd, 2025). Having a market share of 87.53%, its competitors include Indeed (0.99%), Adp (0.90%), Workday Human Capital (0.64%) (6sense, 2025). In India, over 55 million working professionals have LinkedIn profiles; over 1 million company pages; over 350,000 open jobs and over 50,000 skills added by members to their profiles and showcase their professional brands. Software Engineers, System Engineers and Business Analyst were the top jobs hired for during FY 2024-25. (Economic graph team, 2019).

Objective of study

The study focuses specifically on how LinkedIn supports or hinders the job search process from the perspective of individual users actively seeking employment or career advancement. The objectives are:

1. **Analyzing LinkedIn's effectiveness** in helping job seekers find relevant opportunities, connect with recruiters and build professional networks.
2. **Understanding user experiences** related to job application features, profile visibility and value of premium tools.
3. **Identifying common challenges** faced by job seekers on the platform, such as competition, algorithm limitations or engagement barriers.
4. **Exploring user awareness and perception** of alternative platforms or tools that might better support job seekers

Review of Literature

S.NO	TITLE OF STUDY	DATE	MAJOR FINDINGS	METHODOLOGY
1.	Networking via LinkedIn: An examination of usage and career benefits	(Joanna Davis, 2020)	LinkedIn's networking tool has positively impacted the careers of job seekers.	Mixed-mode survey (pen-paper survey with LinkedIn profile).
2.	Is LinkedIn making you more successful? The informational benefits derived from public social media	(Utz, 2015)	Increased usage of social media like LinkedIn can increase social capital in professional domain	Survey based on 3367 people, representative for Dutch online users (1959 were included in actual analysis).
3.	LinkedIn for Searching Better Job Opportunity: Passive Jobseekers' Perceived Experience	(MD Sajjad Hosain, 2020)	LinkedIn is the most preferred tool in all terms (information availability, accuracy, relevance and reliability)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convenience Sampling to select participants • Collection of responses and keywords through group discussion
4.	The inefficacy of LinkedIn? A latent change model and experimental test of using LinkedIn for job search	(Johnson, 2020)	The more individuals use LinkedIn for job search, the worse their job search self-efficacy becomes, the more they become depleted and poorer their success for job search.	Multivariate Latent Change Analysis along with Between-Person experiment.
5.	Social media marketing strategies for career advancements: An analysis of LinkedIn	(McCabe, 2017)	SNS are directly impacting the job search cycle and job search model, creating needs for students to adapt to these changes.	Conceptual framework based on expert secondary content through business database of peer reviewed content.
6.	Building student network with LinkedIn: The potential for connections, internships, and jobs.	(Anon., 2014)	LinkedIn has been very effective for students to learn networking and improve knowledge and even secure jobs.	In - class exercises for 119 college going students over the course of 2 semesters
7.	Social Networks: Advantages and disadvantages of its use in job hunting	(Courelas, 2014)	SNS has both advantages and disadvantages, advantages outweighing. Should be used with caution	Questionnaire based research separate for recruiters and candidates.
8.	The effect of LinkedIn on Deception in Resumes	(Jamie Guillory, 2012)	There is less deception towards pointers like work experience and responsibilities. More deception towards interests and hobbies ⁹ .	119 Participants in a between-subject experiment, aimed at creating a resume in different settings
9.	User trust in social networking services: A comparison of Facebook and LinkedIn	(Shuchih Ernest Chang, 2017)	Factors like effort expectancy, social influence and perceived risk affect user trust on LinkedIn.	Questionnaire were collected from 184 respondents who claimed to have experience of SNS
10.	Understanding professional connections in LinkedIn – A question of trust	(Craig C. Claybaugh, 2013)	Dyadic tie strength is influenced by an individual's disposition to trust and by the trust belief between the respondent and the respondent's last connection made in LinkedIn. Trust in LinkedIn did not influence the relationship.	The method used to evaluate the proposed research model was structural equation modelling using data collected from a questionnaire survey from a random sample of LinkedIn users.

Research Gap

While conducting a comprehensive literature review, the researcher realized that **no recent researches have been conducted in the recent years** regarding the impact of LinkedIn on job seekers amidst the changing job environment. The job market has drastically evolved with increased dependency on virtual platforms, hybrid roles and AI Integration, which is underrepresented in the previous researches. Hence, this research aims to establish coherence with the recent changing business environment and its impact on current job seekers.

While several studies praise LinkedIn's networking and visibility benefits, only one (**Johnson, 2020**) touches on the **negative experiences** such as decreased job search self-efficacy. There's lack of in-depth analysis of **challenges users face** with LinkedIn's job search algorithm, premium features, or recruiter responsiveness.

Despite LinkedIn's substantial presence in India, being the prime application for job seekers, **most prior researches focus on the western populations**. There's a significant gap in understanding how Indian job seekers – especially fresh graduates and mid-career professionals interact with LinkedIn and how effective is it in this unique job market.

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Very few, if any, studies have investigated the **perceived vs. actual value of LinkedIn's Premium features**, despite their wide promotion. Understanding whether these tools truly give users an edge is a valuable unexplored area.

Need of the Study

Despite LinkedIn's dominant presence as a professional networking platform and job search tool, the effectiveness and satisfaction of users, especially job seekers in today's dynamic employment landscape remains underexplored. With rise of remote work, AI-driven job matching and increasing competition for limited roles, the job search and increasing competition for limited roles, the job search process has become more complex and digital than ever before. While past research has highlighted LinkedIn's benefits for networking and information access, there is limited understanding of how the platform currently supports or hinders job seekers' real world goals, particularly in emerging markets like India.

In this evolving context, there is a pressing need to assess whether LinkedIn continues to meet the expectations and needs of job seekers or if gaps in user experience, accessibility, visibility, or engagement are affecting its utility. Additionally, a few studies have evaluated user awareness or perceptions regarding alternative job platforms that may better align with their preferences and aspirations.

1. This study is therefore essential to bridge the research gap and provide insights into:
2. How job seekers currently use LinkedIn,
3. The platform's strengths and shortcomings in helping them find employment,
4. And whether there is a genuine demand for a better or inclusive alternative in job market.
5. By capturing real time feedback and opinions of active job seekers, the study will contribute meaningful knowledge for platform develops and job seeker themselves, enabling more effective strategies in the future

Methodology

Scope of The Study

This study aims to understand the role of LinkedIn as a job search and professional networking platform from the perspective of **active job seekers**. It aims to evaluate the platform's effectiveness in helping users find employment, build meaningful professional connections and navigate the competitive digital job market.

The study is limited to individual users such as:

1. Final year students and recent graduates,
2. Entry level professionals,
3. Mid-career professionals seeking career shifts or advancement.

It specifically explores user experiences with features such as:

1. Job search tools
2. Profile visibility
3. Recruiter Interactions
4. Networking capabilities; and
5. Premium subscription services

Furthermore, the research also aims to examine the user awareness of alternative platforms and experimental features while gathering opinion on whether there is a need for a better or more tailored solution.

The geographic study of the research is India, where LinkedIn has a rapidly growing user base. The study does not cover:

1. Employer/Recruiter perspective
2. Internal business operations or algorithms of LinkedIn
3. Job markets outside of India

Research Design

The study follows a descriptive research design, which is appropriate for systematically collecting and analyzing data to describe the current status and opinions of job seekers using LinkedIn. This approach enables the researcher to quantify user experiences,

identify patterns of behavior and evaluate satisfaction levels with LinkedIn’s features and tools in a structured and measurable manner.

Data Collection

Primary data has been collected using surveys and structured questionnaires distributed online through Google Forms. This method ensures direct interaction with the target audience and facilitates the collection of authentic, first-hand insights into users’ behavior, satisfaction levels, and perceived gaps in LinkedIn’s job search features.

Target Sample

The target population for this research includes active job seekers such as:

1. Students in final year of graduation
2. Fresh graduates
3. Entry-level professionals
4. Mid-career individuals looking for job transition or up skilling opportunities.

Sample Size

A sample size of 75 respondents was selected to maintain manageability and ensure adequate representation for preliminary analysis. This size provides a sufficient base for exploring patterns while remaining feasible within the constraint of time and resources.

Sampling Method

A judgmental (purposive) sampling method was used, where respondents were chosen based on the researcher’s understanding and selection criteria. This technique allowed focused data collection from individuals who are most relevant to the study, i.e. those actively using LinkedIn for job search.

Scaling Techniques

1. To measure attitudes, satisfaction levels and perceptions, the questionnaire included:
2. Likert scales to capture agreement/disagreement with various statements
3. Semantic differential scales to gauge impression of LinkedIn features (e.g., Useful-Not Useful)
4. Open-ended questions to capture a unique point of view of the respondents.

Data Analysis

Collected data was analyzed using Google Forms and Microsoft Excel, leveraging features such as:

1. Frequency Distribution
2. Charts and Graphs
3. Cross-tabulations.

These tools enabled clear visualization and interpretation of trends, helping to draw meaningful conclusions and recommendations.

Analysis

Q1. Age of respondent

Majority of the respondent belonged to the age group of 21-25 (60%), implying the fact that the majority of the responses that were collected, includes entry working professionals and final year college going students. The least percentage of respondents belonged to the age group of 25-29 (9.3%) that included mid-level career professionals

followed by age group 30+ (13.3%) that have a well-established career in corporate with a large amount of exposure. Respondents in the age group of 16-20 accounted for about 17.3%.

Q2. What is your current employment status?

Majority of the respondents were part-time/intern professionals (38.7%) followed by full time working professionals (25.3%) implying that the responses will be majorly from the point of view of those respondents that are active in the corporate sector. 20% of the respondents were self-employed and 9.3% respondents were students who use LinkedIn for additional learning, serving as an important link in the study. Remaining people (6.7%) belonged to others category (Unemployed, on career breaks, etc.)

Q3. What industry do you work in?

This was an open-ended question and many diverse answers were received on this question. Respondents belonged to basic industries such as IT and Software industries to specialized industries such as Astrology, Housing etc. Majority of the people belonged to the IT sector (12), followed by Marketing (4) and so on

Q4. Do you actively use online networking platforms for job seeking? (LinkedIn, Glassdoor, Naukri.com)

Around 77.3% respondents claimed to actively use SNS for job seeking. This implies that the results of the survey will reflect the point of view of respondents that actively use these applications and are quite familiar with their working, reducing the chances of false answers. 13.3% respondent replied with Maybe, followed by 9.3% for response no.

Q5. How effective do you find LinkedIn for job hunting? (Rate 1-5, 1 = Not effective, 5 = Very effective)

31 respondents (41.3%) were neutral about the effectiveness of LinkedIn, implying the fact that they may face some negative effects along with some positive effects of using LinkedIn. However, 23 respondents (30.7%) were on the positive side of using LinkedIn as their go-to app, followed by 7 respondents (9.3%) being extremely satisfied. This implies that the respondents have a positive outlook towards LinkedIn as an app that satisfies their basic needs promptly. Around 14 respondents were on the negative side of using LinkedIn.

Q6. Have you ever been contacted with a recruiter on LinkedIn?

The responses of this question are balanced. Around 36% respondents did get contacted by a recruiter on LinkedIn, however didn't land a job opportunity (Yes 2), followed by 32% respondents that did get contacted and also did get a job interview (Yes 1). In ideal conditions, the respondents belonging to yes (2) should have gotten a job interview, but they didn't, implying the possibility of fake recruitment messages or large amount of competition for one job post. Around 32% didn't get contacted by a recruiter ever.

Q7. If yes, what do you feel is the most important factor for getting a job through LinkedIn?

Majority of the respondents agreed upon having a strong LinkedIn profile (74.6%) (Summary, headlines, skills, background) is the key to getting noticed by a recruiter and getting a job through LinkedIn, underscoring the importance of first impression. 70.4% responses (50) supported that Networking is also the most important factor in securing a job, implying that connections and referrals is equally important in getting a job through LinkedIn. Only 11 responses supported that having LinkedIn Premium is effective for getting a job, implying that spending more on premium isn't the best case, in fact the least favorable solution for getting a job.

Q8. What are some of the biggest challenges you face when using LinkedIn? (Select all that apply)

Majority of the responses (41) agreed that 'too much competition for job postings' is one of the biggest challenges respondents face when using LinkedIn, implying the growing population of the Indian subcontinent. Followed by equal responses (30 each) for two responses 'Hard to connect with recruiters' and 'no response to application by companies', implying the ineffectiveness of companies and recruiters on their end. The least selected response was the use of 'Premium features' that are needed to stand out, implying the ineffectiveness of paying more to stand out as it reaps no benefits.

Q9. How easy is it to contact with recruiters on LinkedIn? (1= very difficult, 5 = very easy)

Majority of the responses were skewed towards Moderate (3), implying that majority respondents feel it isn't easy nor difficult but manageable to contact recruiters on LinkedIn with some effort. Only 8% responses implied that it is extremely difficult to connect with recruiters on LinkedIn. While 26% of the responses were towards the positive side of the ease of connecting recruiters.

Q10. Have you ever encountered fake job postings or scams on LinkedIn?

Majority of the responses (37.3%) were skewed towards the response of 'Occasionally', followed by 32% for 'Yes, frequently' implying that it is common to see fake job postings on LinkedIn. This is alarming and points out the unavailability of appropriate measures to check the credibility of job postings. 30.7% respondents denied encountering any fake job postings.

Q11. Would you consider using a new job-seeking platform, if it had better features?

Majority of the responses were skewed towards the outcome of Yes (80%), implying that the respondents were open to exploring new avenues if they offer better service and features. Only 20% of the respondents showcased the hesitation to try new avenues signifying their comfortableness to LinkedIn.

Q12. What features do you want in a newer job search platform? (Select all that apply)

Around 50 respondents favored both 'easier recruiter-applicant interactions' and 'real time application status features' as the prominent features in a new application, showcasing the growing demand of transparency in the job seeking process and better compatibility options among large amount of job postings on LinkedIn daily. The next most favored option was 'on-spot background checks for recruiters and job seekers' (35 votes), again specifying the need of transparency in the process. This was followed 32 votes for 'industry specific networking options' and 23 votes for 'Emphasis on creativity' during profile building.

Q13. Would you trust AI-based Job matching over traditional applications?

80% of the respondents (60) voted in favor of AI based job matching as it could make job searching more efficient signifying the willingness of respondents to adapt AI in their job seeking process. 17.3% respondents (13) preferred manual job applications as a better form signifying their distrust and unwillingness to choose AI. The questionnaire received an open ended response to this question, the answer being the fact that 'it depends on the authenticity', implying the ethical use of AI as an important factor in a respondents mind.

Q14. Would you like Gamification features (skill badges, achievements levels) in a job seeking platform?

Majority of the respondents (55.4%) were in favour of gamification features as it would make the process more engaging and challenging, followed by 23% of the respondents

that were sceptical about the features, implying that it depends upon the execution. This was followed by 21.6% in the favour of no for the features.

Q15. What type of job-search assistance would you find the most helpful?

34.2% of respondents were in favour of personalized job alerts, implying the need of personalization and comfort during the job seeking process due to large number of job posting daily. This was followed by 'Skill Assessment and Certification Suggestions' (24.7%), implying the need of comprehensive mechanism for personalized skill and certification suggestions to boost career growth. The least favoured vote was for the response of 'Networking Event Recommendation' (4.1%) implying the ineffectiveness of such events for job seekers.

Findings

1. Fake job postings and scams are common in LinkedIn, with 69% of the respondents claiming to come across fake jobs with fake salaries.
2. Majority of respondents feel too much competition for job postings on LinkedIn (54.7%) implying the need for better job posting management on the app.
3. Along with Networking, a strong LinkedIn profile is also considered to be a strong factor for getting a job through LinkedIn.
4. 36% of the respondents voted for not being able to secure a job opportunity despite getting in contact with a recruiter which highlights the inefficiency of the recruiters end, implying the need of more stringent regulations on LinkedIn.
5. Among all the features in an alternative application, Real time application status (66.7%) and easier recruiter-applicant interactions (68%) were the top-most favoured features in an alternative application.
6. Gamification features were considered an ideal experimental feature, with respondents claiming it to be more engaging for the users of the app. (55.4%)
7. Among all the job-assistance features, 'Personalized Job-alerts' (34.2%) and 'Skill assessment and certification suggestions' (24.7%) were among the top favoured votes.

Conclusion

The study highlights that while LinkedIn remains a widely used platform for job search and networking, it falls short in meeting the evolving needs of the job seekers. Key challenges include excessive competition, limited recruiter interaction and presence of fake job postings. The research also explains the ineffectiveness of LinkedIn Premium. There is a clear interest towards alternative platforms offering greater transparency, real-time updates and AI integration. The findings suggest a growing demand for a more user-centric, efficient solutions tailored to Indian employment landscape.

Future Scope of Study

1. Expansion of Sample Size and Diversity: Future research can include a larger and more diverse sample size across different regions, industries, and educational backgrounds to enhance the validity and generalizability of the findings.
2. Inclusion of Employer/Recruiter Perspective: Including views from recruiters and hiring managers would offer a dual-sided understanding of how LinkedIn functions in the recruitment process and where gaps may lie.
3. Comparative Studies with Other Platforms: Future studies could conduct a comparative analysis of LinkedIn versus other job search platforms (e.g., Naukri, Indeed, Glassdoor) to identify which features or models users prefer and why.
4. Platform Usability & Algorithm Evaluation: There is scope for deeper exploration into LinkedIn's algorithm, recommendation systems, and how it affects job visibility, especially for different demographics or industries.

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5. Behavioural & Psychological Insights: Further research could explore the psychological impact of LinkedIn usage, such as motivation, digital fatigue, or job search anxiety, through qualitative or longitudinal methods.
6. Mobile App and Regional Accessibility: As mobile use increases, future studies could examine the usability and effectiveness of the LinkedIn mobile app, especially for users in regional language markets or low-internet zones.

Suggestions for the future Study Majority of the respondents agreed upon facing various issues in LinkedIn, which implies that the company shall make notable changes in their application based user interface. Some notable changes being:

1. Better job posting management
2. Efficient and Personalize Job Alerts
3. Skill Assessment and Certification Suggestions
4. Real time application status
5. Easier recruitment-applicant interactions
6. Better Transparency
7. Effective credibility check mechanisms

All of these features were considered important by respondents to tackle the highly uncertain business environment and the dynamic employment landscape with the rise of competition for job postings among the Indian job market.

Limitation of the Study 1. Limited Sample Size: The study is based on a limited sample size, with a respondent base of only 75 job seekers, which may not be fully representative of the larger population of LinkedIn users across different sectors and regions in India

2. Sampling Bias: The use of Judgmental sampling may introduce bias, as the respondents were selected based upon the researcher's discretion. This may affect the generalizability of the findings.
3. Seeker Perspective: The study focuses on the perspective of job seekers only, and does not include insights from recruiters, HR professionals, or employers, which could provide a more holistic understanding of LinkedIn's effectiveness
4. Platform Specific Analysis: While alternatives are briefly considered, the primary focus remains on LinkedIn, and the study does not delve deeply into comparative analysis with other job platforms like Naukri, Indeed, or Glassdoor.
5. Self-reported Data: The findings are based on self-reported data that might be subject to response biases such as exaggeration, social desirability, or selective recall.

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